

Artificial Intelligence in Banking Sector

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Abstract

Conversion of data in digital format through technology is digitalization .as the banks have embraced digitalization it has resulted in reduction of human errors and has provided convenience to customers reducing time, people have round the clock access to online banking Technology has removed much of the face to face bank-customer interactions like fingerprint readers, card readers and new and emerging and financial technologies ensuring privacy and minimizing or reducing fraud concerns with increasingly innovative technologies .

Banking institutions are working towards delivering their financial services Artificial Intelligence (AI) is fast evolving as the go-to technology for companies across the world to personalize experience for individuals. The technology itself is getting better and smarter day by day, allowing more and newer industries to adopt the AI for various applications. Banking sector is becoming one of the first adopters of AI. And just like other segments, banks are exploring and implementing the technology in various ways.

Keywords: Digitalization, Technology quality standard, Financial services Artificial intelligence

Introduction

Financial services industry due to change of consumer behavior, customer expectations and adoption of technology is going through dramatic changes. Digital banking is now an important feature in today’s world. There is plethora of options that customer can adopt when it comes into banking. The advent of technology has made people to prefer anything online. A special area of innovation – Artificial intelligence and machine learning is the face of advanced technology and people are embracing it in both personal and business banking areas. Two key factors that have influenced this shift is the development of the internet and the dramatic reduction in the cost of technology. Technological if embraced in a right way will generate a banking system for customers and citizens into the future

What is Artificial Intelligence?

By definition, Artificial Intelligence is nothing but the intelligent and proactive actions that devices and applications perform without active human intervention. Such machine led automated as well as intelligent activities are visible on many fronts including machine learning, natural language processing, machine analytics, chatbots, algorithms, etc.

Review of Literature

Secondary data is being used to give a greater understanding and insight into artificial intelligence and to present with challenging demands that are required for banking sector to have competitive edge

Artificial intelligence in Banking Sector:

Incorporating Artificial intelligence in banking sector will help to improve efficiency, keep up with digital trends and satisfy customer demands and can be there for the customers to help them improve their financial lives, which in turn will help banks to pivot their strategies in order to preserve customer loyalty. Banks can use AI to customize products and advertising based on need, life stage, and behavior by combining information from transaction histories, prior inquiries, geolocation, customer search history, and even social media sites. For instance, a bank could analyze a customer’s transaction history to recognize an airline preference and then send a notification via the bank’s mobile app to inform the customer of a new credit card partnership with that airline.

The pace at which companies are investing in artificial intelligence (AI) continues to gain momentum and the financial sector is not immune to this trend. According to research by global management consultancy Accenture, banks that invest in AI and human-machine collaboration tools could boost their revenue by over a third (34 per cent) by 2022.

Advent of AI banking in India

According to Accenture’s recent Accenture Banking Technology Vision 2018 report, 83% of Indian bankers believe that AI will work alongside humans in the next two years — a higher than the global average of 79%. “93% bankers in India said they increasingly use data to drive critical and automated decision-making. More partner-supplied customer data means a higher degree of responsibility for banks. Yet, 77% Indian bankers agree that most firms are not prepared to confront impending waves of corrupted insights from falsified data,” said the report.

Common uses of Artificial Intelligence in Banks

1. ATMs – To detect frauds
2. Security- Spurious emails if any can be tracked to prevent and predict security breaches if any
3. Customer support and help desk – Good customer service and encourage customers to remain loyal
4. Management of wealth –To guide the customers on expected rate of investment
5. Risk analysis – informing customers in risk analysis and elimination of human errors

Challenge and opportunity in Banking sector

1. Scarcity of trained human resources
2. Unavailability of people with science skills background, training programmes are required to improve science skills
3. Mass adoption of Artificial intelligence will lead to grave unemployment problem but it’s going to take a big investment to make that happen. Technology will eliminate jobs that are repetitive and require less human judgement.
4. Advances in Artificial intelligence will definitely will happen even if the banks participate in it or not, it is going to happen.
5. Artificial intelligence can also free employees from mundane tasks so that they can focus on being better in strategizing and doing complex activities.

6. Financial ups and downs are beyond recognition of human minds; however, Artificial intelligence with the use of algorithms can automatically prompt better decisions. AI renders more independent decisions which often results in raised financial growth and preparation for the future.
7. Artificial industry has impacted Banking industry which makes it to keep up with competition and increase their standing. Over the coming years, these systems are only set to become more and more accurate and fast with the continuous innovations and improvements in the field of artificial intelligence.
8. Bank customers are becoming more and more demanding. In the age of Google, Apple, Facebook and Amazon, we have become accustomed to personalized offers building on data that we have voluntarily provided

Critical Challenges

1. Changing consumer dynamics- Friction need to be removed from customers, change should come within and banks have to face more competition and affordable ways need to be done to accomplish tasks
2. Retention of customers- retaining customers is a very big challenge, banks need to meet customers and must always be available to them and solving their problems instantly and providing most innovative and hands on service.
3. Use of Virtual assistance – Banks need to provide assistants who work like chat box and answer queries and solve problems as customers nowadays don't want to wait for an answer, these kinds of interaction happen only if there is a well-defined and integrated platform

The bank's internal systems are made easier to track and deal with individual customers, that is governed and used to serve customers and optimize running the bank.

People with required skills to build and maintain the robots, more data engineers and data scientist are required, an attempt should be made to enhance rather replace existing workforce

How will the Banking sector be affected?

1. Improved and cost effective customer service, playing a role where it is not possible for a human being to bear the burden of all the customers
2. Better management is possible The Artificial Intelligence powered solution can provide a full report with all references and facts, thus helping both the bank and the company.
3. Know our future prospects and returns with a targeted AI solution, you can keep getting continuous updates on various offers available and build on your current assets to increase your returns. Also, you don't have to start from scratch as the AI will do all your work for you. Once you have an AI system in place, it will keep your account safe from market fluctuations.
4. Precise investment information and research- The finance sector is a volatile one, and many a time there and many a time, there are crucial decisions that need to be made. In this case, it is but natural to choose the expert programming of an AI over human predictions and trust the AI's continuous learning methods to forecast better. If the bank has an AI system in place, it can provide all the research and reference along with exact facts and figure to help make the best possible decision which will then be an Invaluable asset in the financial sector and will continue to be in the future

Building a better customer experience

Significant shift in customer expectations is seen over the past few years, the trend is growing stronger as comfort with digital banking grows with disposable incomes, Artificial intelligence will serve with superior insights to their customers’ needs and preferences and giving them ability to tailor their offerings and attract new customers

Conclusion

Artificial intelligence has become a reality today, what we see around is just the beginning we cannot deny that in the years to come it will be crucial and integral part of our life. Banking being an early adopter will grow exponentially in the future, and to stay competitive in this cutthroat environment by revolutionizing and transforming the very face of routine operations They can quickly pinpoint the issues from thousands of log entries which are often time consuming and erroneous when a human mind handles them.

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